

Productive tillers/plant, flag leaf area, and yield/plant of Basmati 370 and NIAB Rice-1 in both environments differed significantly (see table). Plant height did not differ. Performance of the F₁s of Basmati 370/NIAB Rice-1 and NIAB Rice-1/Basmati 370 did not

differ. The F₁s showed heterosis over Basmati 370 for all the traits studied. However, true heterobeltiosis was observed only for plant height.

These results indicate the absence of any extragenic basis of salt tolerance, at least for these two genotypes. □

TTB15-1 is 90 cm tall with intermediate tillering ability and 114-125 d duration. It is awnless, medium-grained, with fully exerted panicles. The 1,000-grain weight is 22.0 g. It has nonglutinous endosperm with translucent white kernels and acceptable cooking quality.

TTB15-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, brown planthopper, and whitebacked planthopper but susceptible to blast. It is resistant to shattering.

In eight transplanting trials in Karimganj and Titabar, yield was 8-36.8% higher than that of check varieties (see table). In on-farm trials, its yield advantage was higher because a low yielding local traditional ahu variety was used as the check. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Release of new rice cultivar Jasmine 85 in USA

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The release of Jasmine 85, a new long-grain rice cultivar, was announced by ARS, U.S. Department of Agriculture and the agricultural experiment stations of Texas, Mississippi, Arkansas, and Louisiana.

Jasmine 85 (IR841) derives from the IRRI cross IR262/Khao Dawk Mali

105. IR262 was from the cross Peta *3/ Taichung Native 1.

Jasmine 85 is an aromatic (scented) rice possessing the flavor and aroma of fragrant rices of Thailand. Average amylose content is 17% and alkali spreading value 6.5. This characterizes Jasmine 85 as a low-amylose, low-gelatinization-temperature type similar to Thai fragrant rices. Typically, cooked grains of Jasmine 85, like those of the Thai fragrant rices, are soft and cohesive with the cooked kernels tending to cling together. □

Medium-duration Taichung Sen Yu 285 released in Sichuan as Chuan Mi 2

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Taichung Sen Yu 285, an International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) entry from Taiwan, evaluated in Sichuan since 1983—at RRI for 3 yr and in regional provincial tests for 2 yr—was released in Mar 1989 as Chuan Mi 2 for cultivation in Sichuan.

Mean grain yield over 3 yr in RRI trials was 7.6 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check (see table). In the 1986-87 regional test for grain quality, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 6% higher than the local check. In 1988 Adaptive Research Trials in three counties, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check.

Chuan Mi 2 is a semidwarf (90-95 cm), heavy-tillering rice with 135-140 d duration. Grain is medium slender, fine and white, with 3.6% amylose and 10.73% protein content. It has 73% milling recovery and good cooking quality.

TTB15-1, a promising rice variety for Assam

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TTB15-1 is a medium-duration variety suitable for transplanted ahu (autumn) season in Assam under rainfed conditions. The variety was developed at RARS from IR24/CR44-118-1 and has been recommended for cultivation in relatively flood-free medium-altitude ricelands.

Grain yield and duration of TTB15-1 in trials in Assam, India, 1984-88.

Year	Location	Growing condition	TTB15-1		Check			
			Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Increase over check (%)
1984	Titabar	Ahu	4.3	115	Ch 63	3.8	111	15
1984	Titabar	Ahu	3.6	123	TTB2-6-1-1	3.2	134	14
1985	Karimganj	Ahu	2.2	116	IR50	1.9	111	17
1986	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	114	IR50	2.2	103	32
1987	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	118	IR50	2.6	111	8
1987	Titabar	Ahu	2.9	124	TTB2-6-1-1	2.4	132	20
1987	Titabar	Sali	4.0	124	Ratna	2.9	116	34
1988	Titabar	Ahu	5.5	125	Ratna	4.0	128	37
	Mean		3.5	120		2.9		23
<i>On-farm trial</i>								
1986	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	2.7	125	Takuguni	1.4	117	97
1988	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	4.2	123	Takuguni	1.9	114	125

Performance of Chuan Mi 2 at the Sichuan RRI in regional tests, and in adaptive research trials. Luzhou, Sichuan, China, 1983-88.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Chuan Mi 2	Local check
<i>Rice Research Institute trial</i>		
1983	7.2	6.9
1984	8.3	8.0
1985	7.2	6.4
Mean	7.6	7.1
<i>Regional test in Sichuan Province</i>		
1986	7.7	7.4
1987	7.1	6.6
Mean	7.4	7.0
<i>Adaptive research trial</i>		
1988	7.4	6.9

Chuan Mi 2 was screened in the greenhouse for resistance to important diseases of the area: it is resistant to blast. □

TTB14-1 fits ahu (autumn) season in double-cropped areas of Assam

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TTB14-1, a semidwarf variety derived from CRM13-3241/Kalinga 2 at RARS, Titabar, is suitable for ahu (autumn) season in rainfed high to medium-altitude lands in Assam. Optimum sowing and transplanting dates are Mar/Apr and Apr/May, respectively.

In transplanting experiments 1984-88, average TTB14-1 yield was 3.4 t/ha. This variety has been gaining

Table 1. Characteristics of TTB14-1. Assam, India, 1984-88.

Plant height	95 cm
Panicle length	23.0 cm
Grain type	Medium
1000-grain weight	22.0 g
Grain length	7.89 mm
Grain length/width	2.94
Kernel length	5.75 mm
Kernel length/width	2.36
Kernel color	White

popularity among farmers because of its high yield potential and because its 110-120 d growth duration enables

planting in double-cropped areas.

General characteristics and yield are given in Tables 1 and 2. □

Table 2. Yield and duration of TTB14-1 at different locations. Assam, India, 1984-88.

Year	Location	Season ^a	TTB14-1		Check		
			Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
1984	Titabar	Ahu	3.1	118	Ch63	1.7	113
1986	FTS, Gelapukhuri	Ahu	2.5	117	Takuguni	1.4	117
1987	Titabar	Sali	3.0	110	Ratna	2.9	118
1988	Titabar	Ahu	4.7	120	Ratna	4.0	128
1988	FTS, Gelapukhuri	Ahu	4.0	110	Takuguni	1.9	114
		Mean	3.4	115		2.4	118

^aAhu = fall, sali = winter.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of boiling water treatment on germination and growth of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Dormancy in *S. rostrata* seeds can be broken by boiling water treatment. We studied the effect of length of boiling water treatment on germination and growth in a pot experiment Jan-Mar 1989.

Well-developed seeds (25/set) were treated with 98 °C water for 0 to 75 s at 15-s intervals, with 3 replications. Seeds were sown in pots filled with Vertisol and grown for 65 d with regular watering. Plants were uprooted and root and shoot portions separated and dried in a hot air oven at 65-70 °C to a uniform moisture content.

Treatment with boiling water significantly improved germination (see table). Duration of treatment did not significantly affect dry matter production. □

Influence of boiling water (98 °C) seed treatment on germination and dry matter production of *Sesbania rostrata* at Dharwad, India.

Treatment	Plants/pot (no.)	Germination (%)	Shoot dry weight (g/pot)	Root dry weight (g/pot)	Total dry weight (g/pot)
Control (no treatment)	1.0	4	1.47	0.30	1.77
Treatment with 98 °C water for					
15 s	15.3	62	4.93	0.83	5.76
30 s	17.3	70	6.50	1.10	7.60
45 s	19.0	76	5.75	0.90	6.65
60 s	19.0	76	5.50	0.96	6.46
75 s	19.3	78	5.98	0.81	6.79
SE±	0.4		0.75	0.12	0.85
LSD (P=0.5)	1.4		2.36	0.36	2.69